

PLOT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE EPISODES “FARKHAD AND SHIRIN” BY ALISHER NAVOIY AND LAMIA CHALABI

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Abstract. This article is about a comparative analysis of the plot features of the epics “Farkhad and Shirin” of Alisher Navoi and the Turkish poet Lamii Chalabi. It examines the features of traditionalism and individuality in the work of both creators, based on examples of similar and different aspects in the plots. The specificity of the epics is revealed.

Keywords: *odobi tasnif, “Khamsa”, rhythm, basmala, character, dynamic, plot.*

In Eastern classical literature, each creator has his own style, and the creators wrote works of art that do not repeat each other in traditional themes and forms. Although such works of the lyrical-epic type are independent, translated, free translations, the personality of the creator is clearly manifested in the plot of the work.

According to the creation of series of epics "Khamsa" in Eastern literature, it has a large scope, and the plots that have acquired a traditional form (moral classification) appear in the works of Khamsa writers in a traditional and individual form. These are dynamically visible in image, form, content and prosody.

Since initial answers to Nizami’s “Khamsa” in Persian literature were written by Khusrav Dehlavi, and in Turkish literature - by Alisher Navoi. Both creators fully followed the traditions of Nizami Ganjavi. The predefined traditional themes, the poetic rhythm, clearly follow the poetic prosody, while the shape and prosody are completely preserved. In Persian-Tajik literature, Khoju Kermaniyyi, and in Turkic literature, Hamdullah Hamdi changed the subject and poetic dimensions in “Khamsa”.

Nevertheless, Abdurahman Jami, being a Sufi poet, did not want to write epics praising the rulers. Abdurakhman Jami changed the content, themes, and prosody order existing in the epics. By this time, he had added two more new epics to the Khamsa that consists of five epics. This is how the traditionalism and individuality inherent in the style of the creators appeared in the epics.

In particular, such places are noticeable in the epic “Farhad and Shirin” by Alisher Navoi and Lamia Chalabi, in which we are studying. Turkish poet Lamiy Chalabi follows his teacher in all directions in this Navoi-inspired epic. Navoi’s influence on Lamia Chalabi is felt throughout the work, both in terms of form, mode of expression, and in terms of plot and characters.

While in Navoi the early couplet begins with Arabic words, the Koran and passages from hadith, and in Lamia the same style was used. But when such places are expressed in Navoi in a hidden state, in a poetic form, Lamia will consider it permissible to bring them directly into line. For example

In Navoi’s style:

Bihamdik fath abvob ul-maoni,

Nasib et ko ‘ngluma fath o ‘lmak oni.

Ko ‘zumga ul eshik quflin radid et,

Aning fathig ‘a kilkimni kalid et.[A.Navoiy, 2020: 4]

Lamia Chalabi’s style:

Bede'nâ bi ismik'ellâhümme nazmen

Fe-yessir nahve sübli'r-rüşdi 'azmen...

Îlâhî 'ışkuş ile zinde-dil kıl

Senüñ nûruñla saña müstedil kıl [Hasan Ali Esir, 2017: 28]

In both works, the development of events, the character of the figures, the composition of the figures, roles, time and space are presented in the same state. The main plot of the work begins with chapter XII, and up to this point we can witness in both creators very special forms and themes, a way of expressing poetic thought, a system of images.

The second section of the work, that is, the part preceding the beginning of the main events, the Turkish poet wrote ode in the form of “Shahadat kalimasi”, which used a completely different form than Navoi. At the beginning of each chapter, munjaat to Allah is given in the form of masnavi, a poem in the form of tavhid and again lyrical passages in the form of masnavi.

In the epic of Lamia, the Prophet Muhammad (S.A.V.), nat and hymn, is quoted in the ode in the form of four caliphas. Unlike Navoi, the Turkish poet violated the logical sequence in his work, the roles of the heads came in a mixed state. If in Navoi's work there is a mention of the caliphs in the epic “Lison ut-tair”, then in Lamia's work in chapter VI, the four caliphs are mentioned in 189 bytes, 378 couplets. With this, the Turkish poet changed the subject.

There is a slight difference in the places associated with the main events of the work, Farhad and Shirin, Khusrav, Mehinbon, Shapur. The development of events follows the same plot as that of Alisher Navoi, except for a few details. For both creators, the process went on in parallel. The events that begin at the beginning of the story with the fact that the ruler of the country Chin is childless, poetically continue with the birth of a boy.

Lamia left this position unchanged in his work. The fact that the ruler of the Chin country constantly prays to God for children, distributes donations, fathersless fathers, hunts for the childless like him, does not change in both works. The next section explains how to name a child and its qualities. We can see that the Turkish poet even brought poems from Navoi to this place.

In Navoi's style:

Firoq-u rashk-u hajr-u oh ila dard,

Biror harf ibtidodin aylabon fard.[A.Navoiy, 2020: 49]

Lamia Chalabi's style:

Firâk u reşk ü hicr ü âh ile derd

Birer harf ibtidâdan eyleyüp ferd[Hasan Ali Esir, 2017: 63]

And here Lamias completely borrowed the template from Navoi. The choice of the initials of the words farak, jealousy, Hajr, Oh and dard, which are put as names for the child, their transformation into the fate of Farhad, the whole image associated with it - all this forms have an exact parallel. The poet, borrowing the plot from Navoi, cites precisely the fact that Farhad began walking at the age of one, spoke fluently at the age of three, was interested in the science of disasters, and learned Abjad's account in one day. Lamia follows Navoi, who describes Farhad as a perfect man, considering it acceptable to bring him as his own, who learned to read and write in three months and memorized the Koran in a year. They can also include places related to how he becomes an all-encompassing mature guy when he turns ten. Describing Farhad, the creator described that since the age of 11 he had studied religious and secular sciences, and now it was his turn to fight falling, javelin and bow throwing, and it was Navoi who followed his example in this regard.

In the two following chapters, a parallel is also given with the burning of Farhad in the fire of Ishk, the rescue of the son of the ruler of the Chin country from these sufferings, the construction of four palaces named after the four seasons in order to distract attention.

In Navoi's style:

*Laqabda biri Boniy, biri Moniy,
Muni ko'rgan tasavvur aylab oni.
Qilib me'morliq Boniy ishin fosh,
Kelib Moniy Xito mulkida naqqosh.* [A.Navoiy, 2020: 59]

Lamia Chalabi's style:

*Lakabda biri Mânî biri Bânî
Gören bunı tasavvur eyler ani
Kaçan bu ursa bir bünyâda desti
Felek kadri bulurdu yüz şikesti*[Hasan Ali Esir, 2017: 67]

Farhad's stone carving with Koran and mastery of this art at a high level, masterful study of the science of patterns with Moni, scenes of Farhad's three-month rest in each of these four palaces, built in four years, are depicted in parallel positions in both creative works. The subsequent chapters of both works are both general and identical in nature, continuing and ending in parallel.

There are also changes that Lamia Chalabi made to the composition and plot of the work, the earliest of which is the chapter "Basmala", which reveals the meanings of the letters "Bismillahir Rachmanir rahim". In fact, this chapter, which is an introduction to the Khamsa epics, is also called the "chapter of the Basmala" because it is dedicated to the poetic interpretation of the verse "Bismillahir Rohmanir Rahim" ("I begin with the name of the good and merciful Allah"). We find this in Alisher Navoi's epic "Khairat ul-Abror". In general, the predecessors had a tradition of starting "khamsa" with the verse "Bismillah", and all khamsa creators, starting with Nizami, began their words with this verse.

It was only by Navoi that this chapter became an independent chapter of the Basmala, that is, this chapter was entirely based on the verse "Bismillah". In Navoi, this amounts to 3 chapters separately, and in Lamia Chalabi - only 1 chapter. But in Navoi's epic "Farhad and Shirin" there is no separate chapter about this, since it is divided according to the expression in the early epic. Lamia also explained what the letters "basmala" mean after he said that it is necessary to read "Basmala" with "Ikhlas" and "blessing" in part 1 of "Farhad and Shirin".

As another distinctive place in the epic of Lamia Chalabi, it is described how the masons did in one day what they could not do for three years, Farhad arranged a big feast for Mehinbon and Shirin after they broke the stones and poured water "Ayn-ul-hayat", and dusk came to the feast and the whole Armenian land:

*Mu'azzam şehrdür hemçün Beniyye
Sevâdı Şâm u nâmi Ermeniyye*[Hasan Ali Esir, 2017: 115]

This feast is not in the works of Alisher Navoi. This section is illustrated with exaggerated stories. Describing the party, the poet refers to the charming servants of the mansion and the castle, their dazzling plates and bowls, the chefs, the wonders at the banquet. Lamia Chalabi describes a list of Ottoman Turkish dishes of the 16th century, Turkish customs dating back to his time, and provides information about them.

By translating Masnavi into Anatolian Turkish, reflecting the peculiarities of Chigatai literature, Lamia includes aspects related to Anatolian literature and language in his works. The names of the country, region and place mentioned in the section where mulkoro built four palaces at the request of the kagan, and Farhad admired Koran's skill while observing these palaces, are missing from Navoi's works. Elsewhere, the epic of Lamia mentions that the palaces were built far apart from each other from building materials brought from countries such as China, Algeria, Khorasan and Iraq.

Unlike Navoi, the construction of palaces is depicted in the works of the Turkish poet with extreme exaggeration. That the craftsmen brought from China and Hito dug the foundations of the palaces to the constellation of the bull, that the head of each palace ascends to the star of the constellation Ursa Major, that a stone rain falls from the earth to the sky, that the shadow from the head of each palace reaches the Moon and the sun, that the Sun, stars and heavens move equally for the construction of palaces, that Earth and sky work together even at night.

The image of the Moon weighing lime, such impossible things as mixing this solution with water, the Cup of Fate, the stars pouring stones on the mixed solution every morning, the Milky Way carrying straw from happiness, the sun giving cups, the image of the Moon shining with the marbles of these palaces belong only to the work of Lamia.

Finally, fate comes to these palaces under construction as an architect, zuhala as a builder, Dabb-i ekber as a manager, Ramih as a keeper, Zuhra and Mushtari as a business manager, Utorud as a secretary, and they do not meet in Navoi's work. To these vivid narratives, the party table above should also be added.

Lamia makes other changes to the story. It is known that Farhad was not executed in Navoi's work, the same part is in Lamia: Khusrav falls ill, sending Farhad to his death. Everyone in the palace associates this condition with Farhad's innocence, Farhad's execution is canceled, and Khusrav regains his health.

In the Navoi epic, the deceiver tells Farhad that Mehinbon and Khusrav are friends and therefore Khusrav is with Shirin, which is the reason for his death. Upon receiving this news, Farhad tells the lying woman that all his hope has faded, and tries to get up, but cannot. He falls to the ground and dies.

In Navoi, one of Bonu's relatives becomes the ruler of Armenia. Grave of Farhad turns into a shrine, and Bahram and Shapur are adjacent to the tomb of Farhad. That's how the story ends.

The next chapter of Navoi is devoted to evaluating the talent, personality of the scientist and the pedigree of Shah Gharib Bahadur, a descendant of Temur Khan, to science. It is explained that a person is worthless if he does not do anything useful, even if he has lived the whole life of Noah. However, in Lamia, Shapur is depicted as the ruler of Armenia, and after Farhad's death Bahram completely loses touch with the world, devoting all his time to worship, and Shemun becomes a follower of the priest. He asks her to interpret the dream to the priest of Shemun, and conversations ensued between them.

Finally, Shamun ends his word by saying that the truth has appeared in the heart of Monk Bahram. That's how the story ends. The story is completed in Navoi in the fifty-second chapter, and in Lamia in the fifty-third. In both works, the last chapters are the final parts of the work. These sections are completely different from each other. Poetic weighing the plot in the epics for analysis revealed:

In Navoi's epic "Khairat ul-Abror", the narrator also appears in Lamia's epic "basmala Babi". Also, the "zikh of the caliphs" is mentioned in this epic, found in the epic "Lison ut-Tair". The construction of palaces other than Navoi is described in the Lamia exaggeratedly, the names of places not found in Navoi's work are mentioned. A banquet in honor of Farhad, who dug a ditch, Ottoman Turkish dishes in it, cultural features that are completely absent from Navoi's work.

The scenes related to the death of the main characters were also presented differently by both creators. In Navoi, the main events end in chapter 52, and in Lamia - in chapter 53. The last chapter of the saga is different for both creators.

In conclusion, we can say that although the epic of Lamia Chalabi "Ferhad ila Shirin" is mentioned at the beginning of the work as a translated work, there are places in it in the form of a free translation, but due to the transfer and conversion of bytes, a fair question arises whether this is a translation or a free translation.

Due to the plot of the work, the originality of the texts, and the genre perfection, this work can be attributed to a free translation. This is relevant and important from the point of view of modern Navoi science and the influence of Navoi on Ottoman Turkish literature. Such pressing issues facing our science will serve as a basis for further research.

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